

Effectiveness of Laboratory Method in the Teaching of Biological Science Module One Students at The Eldoret National Polytechnic, Kenya

Carozone Nafula Sitati¹ & Dr. Dinah Samikwo²

¹ Department of Applied Sciences, The Eldoret National Polytechnic

² Department of Education Sciences, University of Eldoret

*Corresponding author's Email: sitaticarozone@gmail.com

Submission Date: Oct 3, 2024; **Revised Submission:** Dec 9, 2024; **Publication Date:** April 18, 2025

ABSTRACT

Laboratory teaching methods have long played a central role in the effectiveness of teaching the biological science curriculum among learners. However, the lecture style has also been successful in educational institutions at all levels. Trainers at Technical Vocational Education Training (TVET) institutions in Kenya employ both lecture and laboratory teaching approaches, yet frequently, the methodologies are to blame for poor results. The study's objective was to assess the efficiency of lectures versus laboratory methods of teaching biological sciences module one students at The Eldoret National Polytechnic to identify the most effective method for improving trainees' performance. A total of 78 trainees selected through purposive and census sampling constituted the sample size. A pilot study was undertaken for the accuracy and reliability of the instruments, obtaining the correlation coefficient scores of 0.847. Quasi-experimental research using pre- and post-test was employed. T-test, mean, and standard deviation were used in analyzing results. The outcome indicated a significant difference in the two methods of teaching ($p=0.000$). In terms of students' performance on test examinations, the study concludes that the laboratory method was superior to the lecture method. It is therefore recommended that trainers in TVET institutions use both lecture and laboratory methods in teaching biological sciences through adopting a competence-based education training (CBET) curriculum within the two methods. The entire practice will enable students to get certificates that are pertinent to industry requirements, workplace performance standards, and become the best in the world.

Keywords: Effectiveness, Laboratory Method, Biological Science, Module One

1. INTRODUCTION

The educational system in Kenya places a strong emphasis on assisting students in developing the collaboration, creativity, and competency required for the twenty-first century. A competency-based curriculum (CBC) has been adopted by the current educational ministry to fulfill the goals of Vision 2030 for science, technology, and innovation (Nyaboke, 2021). The new CBC system offers a smooth transition from Basic Education to TVET due to students having specialized in the relevant fields at the Senior Secondary School level, including dual certification, leading some programs in the Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) sector to adopt Competency Based Education training (CBET), which is closely aligned to the CBC approach (Kerubo, 2023). Lecture method a teacher-centered approach, which continually informs students of what they should learn in class, and laboratory method of teaching which gives students the chance to reflect on, discuss and solve real issues has been tremendously been used as instructional approaches for biological courses in different educational levels around the world (Ramsden, 2003).

Chege (2013) revealed that biological science courses in TVET institutions focus on equipping the student with sufficient knowledge, both theoretical and practical, through exemplary teaching methods by the trainers, to produce graduates with well-polished knowledge and skills to meet the labor market, however, most methods of teaching are not very effective. The methods are teacher-centered with little hands-on practical, resulting in poor performance in Summative exams. Trainers in Kenya use both lecture and laboratory teaching approaches, yet frequently the methodologies are to blame for poor results, raising a lot of concerns, especially with the low number of students getting certification after sitting for the KNEC exam. Furthermore, research has not yet been done on the effectiveness of laboratory versus lecture methods of teaching biological sciences to students at The Eldoret National Polytechnic, Uasin Gishu County; thus, this study is an attempt along these lines to identify the best teaching methods for biological science courses at The Eldoret National Polytechnic.

1.1 Problem of the statement

The problem of underperformance of students in Biological sciences at TVET institutions has raised concerns, especially with the low number of students getting certification after sitting for the KNEC exam. On the whole, there is an urgent need for researchers to concentrate on finding solutions to the best pedagogy method to prevent students' poor performance and the development of negative attitudes towards the Biological science courses in TVET institutions. The table shows students' performance for technical courses in applied biology and lab sciences based on the examination office report at The Eldoret National Polytechnic in the year 2021.

Table 1: Performance of students in KNEC technical exams

Courses	Summative Results (KNEC)% Pass
Diploma in Applied Biology	48. 2%
Diploma in Laboratory Science Technology	47.6%

Source: Examination Office, The Eldoret National Polytechnic (2021)

The statistic indicates that the results for the diploma in applied biology and laboratory science technology are underperforming, with the mean percentage rate of 48.2% and 47.6%, respectively. The table indicates a less than 50% pass mark for students sitting the KNEC technical examination in the courses sampled. As a result, this finding justifies the need for this research by comparing the effectiveness of lectures to the laboratory method of teaching biological science to module one students at The Eldoret National Polytechnic in Uasin Gishu County, Kenya. The goal of this research was to find the best pedagogy method to prevent students' poor performance in biological science courses in TVET institutions.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

To compare the effectiveness of lectures versus laboratory methods in teaching biological science, as measured by students' performance in the exam and test scores.

1.3 Hypothesis

H₀₁ There is no significant difference between lectures versus laboratory methods in teaching biological science students based on the exam test score performance.

1.4 Justification of the Study

Since gaining independence until now Kenya has experienced transformations in its education system. Kenya as a country is steadily progressing to enhance the quality of education, the Kenyan government emphasizes on best teaching methodology in TVET institutions to establish educational guidelines. The aim is to nurture educated individuals who possess a broad range of biological science content that meets the outside world from the classroom and are self-independent and move with the requirements of the labour market. In this study conducted at the Eldoret National Polytechnic, the research focused on exploring teaching practices within the realm of education policy. Moreover, by employing the best teaching methods in TVET institutions, it will continuously upgrade the student learning outcomes and foster academic excellence. The objective was to identify whether lectures or laboratory methods of instruction are effective in educating students pursuing biological science courses, Therefore, the study compared the lecture versus laboratory method of teaching based on the students' test score performance.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Technical Vocational Education Training (TVET) institutions throughout the world have been focusing on lecture-based strategies, and over the years, many unique teaching strategies have evolved, with the teaching techniques being significantly impacted by the accessible instructional resources (Elkhidir, 2020). It was found that the majority of biology teachers preferred to use the lecture and chalk talk methods, which prevented students from mastering the subject thoroughly. The majority of teachers were found to be competent and skilled at using a variety of teaching techniques, but because of the large class sizes and lack of time, they were forced to use the lecture and question-and-answer format instead of the other methods that were suggested. Due to the huge class sizes and poor laboratory training

equipment at the TVET institution in Kenya, tutors mostly employed lectures, demonstrations, work-based learning, and discussions (Anindo et al., 2016). In research by Hawkins and Phelps (2013) comparing the lecture technique to the laboratory method of instruction, the findings revealed that students learned more after using both the lecture and laboratory methods, with students scoring higher when the lecture approach was used. First-year biology students used the labs for tutorials and workshops, where they were divided into smaller groups and actively participated in hands-on practicals that aided in their overall understanding of a problem (Downs et al., 2015). Despite this finding, it was clear that lectures had their place as well. Athuman's (2017) research points out that students who took biological sciences courses using the laboratory method approach scored better than those who took them using the lecture method.

The findings also showed that using hands-on learning activities helped students develop their science process skills. Findings from Willitter et al. (2013) in Kenya revealed that trainers usually employed lecture techniques during class instruction to assist students in finishing the curriculum before end-of-semester exams, instead of adopting laboratory teaching, which takes a lot of time to finish the curriculum. However, the main problems with the TVET curriculum to date are that the curriculum and structure are not matched to industry needs, so graduates are thought to lack the necessary skills. This supply orientation is a significant problem that has consequently contributed to the high rate of youth unemployment (Anderson, 2009). The demands of society have always been a major factor in the advancement of science, the desire to make people's lives better, not forgetting economic progress. Any civilization can only advance when the people are in good health. Sciences have given rise to the areas of dairy, poultry, agriculture, veterinary medicine, microbiology, and biochemistry. It makes people self-reliant, assisting them in developing professional attitudes and technical proficiency (Downs et al., 2015).

Finally, in Kenya, the focus of the educational system's pedagogy skills is on helping students acquire the teamwork, creativity, and competence necessary for the 21st century. To achieve the vision 2030 of science, technology, and innovation, the present educational ministry's goal is to adopt a competency-based curriculum (CBC), 2-6-6-3, announced in 2019. For students to become creative thinkers and expand their knowledge and abilities, they must actively participate in class (Nyaboke, Kereri & Nyabwari, 2021). The new CBC system provides a smooth transition from Basic Education to TVET, and some programs in colleges have adopted Competency-Based Education training (CBET), which is closely aligned to the CBC approach; this has ignited great support for the demand of TVET institutions in Kenya (Kerubo, 2023).

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Study Research Design

The design of the study was quasi-experimental design. This design was utilized since students who participated in the study were found in intact classes, making random assignment to treatment groups impossible. It consisted of pre-test and post-test in order to know the effect

of Student Achievement. Two groups got care utilizing the laboratory and lecture instruction methods.

Table 2: Experimental Design

Groups	Pretest	Treatment	Posttest
1	A1	A	A2
2	B1	B	B2

Note:

A: The experimental group using the lecture method

B: The experimental group using the laboratory method

A1, B1: Pre-test in the Experimental groups

A2, B2: Posttest in the Experimental groups

The study had treatment that were applied by one tutor for teaching diploma in applied biology students. Group one received a pre-test on the selected topic after which they were taught by the lecture method same to group two had a pretest after which they were taught by laboratory method. After being taught all the two groups received a posttest. The results for each test were recorded.

3.2 Study Location

The study was conducted at the Eldoret National polytechnic which is located in Uasin Gishu County Rift valley province 5 kilometers from the Eldoret town. The college Students enrollment stands at total of over 13,000 and offers quite a number of courses under various departments.

3.3 Target Population

The target population for this study was all 6 courses in the department of biology, the 870 students of Biological Science, and the 20 trainers.

3.4 Sample Size

The study adopted purposive sampling in the identification of the applied biology course, same to one trainer from the biological science department to help achieve research objectives. Census sampling was used, which gathered all the 78 students of module one applied biology, for the provision of satisfactory response rates. As stated in Table three, 78 students from an applied biology class and one teacher participated in the study.

Table 3: Sample size

Courses	No. of students	No. of trainers
Applied Biology	78	1
Total	78	1
Percentage	98.7	1.3

3.5 Research Instruments

The research used a number of instruments, including a pre-test, a treatment post-test, and questionnaires.

3.5.1 Pre-test assessment

For this study, the researcher designed pretest instruments for assessing the dependent variables with selected questions on gram staining and culture media topics using define, discuss, describe, and short-answer questions. The instrument, pretest versions used 50 test items based on the Bloom taxonomy in assessing the subjects' knowledge, application, and understanding of the topics. Target topics questions tested included, for example, defining gram staining and culture media. Learners were also asked to describe the Gram-stain Procedure of gram-negative bacteria. The test was then administered at the start of the second week of the term to 78 students of applied biology.

3.5.2 Treatment

For this study, the researcher designed the treatment on two topics of Gram stain and culture media through the preparation of lesson plans, which the trainers applied the lecture and laboratory method in teaching the two groups from the applied biology class before the posttest exam was administered.

3.5.3 Post-test assessment

To determine if the approaches were successful for this study's objectives, the researcher created a post-test instrument that included define, discuss, describe, and short response questions on gram staining and culture media subjects. Target topics questions tested had a different version of setting with multiple forms completely different from a pretest question and included, for example, "what colour is gram stain bacteria", and "in gram stain, what reagent are used", learners were also asked to explain steps involved in preparation of nutrient agar. Despite teaching the same topics, according to Sanders (2019), teachers shouldn't evaluate students using posttests that contain the same questions they encountered in the pre-test. Doing so can result in inaccurate data because a student's progress cannot always be attributed to the skills they have developed if they are already familiar with the test questions. Thus, the posttest administered to students should include a variety of question types.

3.6 Piloting

The pilot study was conducted at the Rift valley technical institute, sample for pilot study consisted of 15 students and one trainer, the participants in piloting were not involved in the main research. The study enabled the researcher to pre-test the research instruments and be able to identify design issues and evaluate a study's feasibility, practicality, resources, time, and cost before the main research was conducted.

3.7 Validity

To check the content validity, the instruments were given to the research supervisors and other experts in the Department of Biological Science at The Eldoret National Polytechnic to validate the instruments. They checked on the instruments' content coverage based on the study parameters. According to the experts' comments and judgment, the researcher improved on the instruments.

3.8 Reliability of Research Instruments

The researcher gave a pretest and posttest to 78 trainees and then gave the same type of test, two weeks later, to the same 78 learners. The pretest-posttest scores were then subjected to Spearman's correlation test using SPSS. The Correlation Coefficient between the two sets of scores was 0.847. Since this correlation is greater than 0.80, the researcher concluded that the test had good test-retest reliability.

3.9 Data Analysis

Data was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize, compare, and explain results from experimental and control groups in terms of mean score and standard deviation. Inferential statistics; a t-test was used to determine if the two groups differ significantly among themselves at $\alpha = 0.05$.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 5: Students' mean and standard deviation in pre-test

Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Pretest lecture	39	59.641	10.145
Pretest laboratory	39	60.256	9.5991

Table 5 presents means and standard deviations value of lecture and laboratory pretest. As indicated, students in the pretest lecture group had a mean score of 59.641 while those in the pretest laboratory group had a mean score of 60.256. The findings indicate that the two groups were slightly different in terms of their pre-test scores.

Table 6: T-test for comparing groups in terms of pre-test

Groups	T	df	p-value
Pretest lecture	36.714*	37	$p \leq 0.01$
Pretest laboratory	39.202*	37	$p \leq 0.01$

In comparing the results of the two methods, the study results showed that there was a significant difference in means between the two methods of teaching applied biology ($p \leq 0.01$). Post-test was given to the participants after the treatment period, Table 5 presents the results.

Table 7: Students' mean and standard deviation in post-test

Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Posttest lecture	39	73.590	9.0778
Posttest laboratory	39	77.615	9.3178

Students in the posttest lecture group had a mean score of 73.590, whereas those in the posttest laboratory group received a mean score of 77.615 as shown in table 5. The results show that the post test scores of the two groups were somewhat distinct.

Table 8: T-test for comparing groups in terms of post-test

Groups	T		p-value
Posttest lecture	50.626*	37	p≤0.01
Posttest laboratory	52.019*	37	p≤0.01

Source: Field data (2023)

In comparing the results of the two methods, the study showed that there was a significant difference in means between the two methods of teaching applied biology ($p \leq 0.01$). This suggests that when used in instruction, the two approaches are different. The researcher believes that since, laboratory method is commonly employed in Technical vocational education institutions in Kenya for practical topics, it might be the reason for the students achieving high scores with the teaching method. The findings are in agreement with the Crowe et al. (2008) study, which looked at laboratory activities and lectures in middle school educational settings. A pretest on categorization about taxonomy was given to 93 learners. Thirty of the students worked on a categorization inquiry lab. The remaining pupils took part in the lecture method. At the end of the unit, a posttest was given, and four months later, a third test. A statistically significant performance difference on the posttest scores was shown by statistical analysis using t-tests.

The research finding is also supported by Nnorom (2016), whereby, according to the study findings, students who were taught using an investigative laboratory technique outperformed those who were taught using the lecture style. The results of the study showed that employing an investigative laboratory method to teach learners helps them develop good science skills and engage in active learning, making them apply all their senses and other talents to their learning more than they would have if they had been less engaged in class activities and equipment manipulation. When students participate in class activities, they learn more effectively. However, the findings of this study contradict the results of Matz (2012), where in his research the students who were taught using the lecture technique outsmarted those who were engaged in laboratory method of teaching resulting into the lecture method being ranked the first most effective, followed by laboratory approach of instruction being the second. The researcher explains that the lecture style of education was more time efficient than the laboratory approach for conveying fundamental knowledge, which is great for both clever and average students.

In addition, the purpose of this study was to determine whether taking a pretest right before teaching would increase students' performance on a subsequent posttest. According to the findings, the majority of participants in this study were able to focus better throughout lectures and laboratory tasks following the pretests, which boosted their performance on the posttest. The recognition of their strengths and weaknesses after the pretest may be the cause. Thus, giving pretests before lectures and laboratory instruction would boost students' attention, interest, and enthusiasm to listen and participate in lectures and laboratory instruction. These perceptions of better performance after the pretest were confirmed to be true by post-test results in the study. This finding is in agreement with the findings of Shivaraju et al. (2017), which showed that there was significant improvement in the recipient's knowledge after pretest- Having obtained a result of 35.9% and 64.10% in a pretest after which the scores were improved in post-test to 53.35% and 78.21% respectively. The study suggests that pre-tests might provide students with direction and motivation.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

According to the study's findings, the laboratory way of teaching was more successful than the lecture technique in terms of student performance on the pretest and posttest. For the improvement of good performance in class as well as outside the classroom, Kenya, a developing nation, should involve more students in the study of biological sciences by problem-solving techniques through practical skills.

5.2 Recommendations

- 1 Teachers/lecturers require a competence-based education training (CBET) curriculum in biological science teaching techniques. This may be done through participating in workshops, benchmarking, and seminars for trainers to remain up to date on new advancements in scientific teaching.
- 2 Departments of biological sciences ought to have access to their funds to build laboratories and purchase laboratory equipment to boost the government funding to TVET institutions.

REFERENCES

- Anderson, D. (2009). Productivism and ecologism: changing dis/courses in TVET. In *Work, learning and sustainable development: Opportunities and challenges* (pp. 35-57). Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands.
- Anindo, I., Mugambi, M., & Matula, D. (2016). Training equipment and acquisition of employable skills by trainees in public technical and vocational education and training institutions in Nairobi County, Kenya. *Training*, 3(4), 103-110.
- Athuman, J. J. (2017). Comparing the effectiveness of an inquiry-based approach to that of a conventional style of teaching in the development of students' science process skills.
- Chege, N. W. (2013). Innovative methods of teaching youth polytechnic students in Kenya.
- Crowe, A., Dirks, C., & Wenderoth, M. P. (2008). Biology in bloom: Implementing Bloom's taxonomy to enhance student learning in biology. *CBE—Life Sciences Education*, 7(4), 368-381.

- Downs, C. T., & Wilson, A. L. (2015). Shifting to Active Learning: Assessment of a First-Year Biology Course in South Africa. *International Journal of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education*, 27(2), 261-274.
- Kerubo, J. (2023). Analysis of Kenya's progress toward a knowledge-based society. *Journal of Education and Practices*. 3(3), 27-44.
- Matz, R. L., Rothman, E. D., Krajcik, J. S., & Banaszak Holl, M. M. (2012). Concurrent enrollment in lecture and laboratory enhances student performance and retention. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 49(5), 659-682.
- Nnorom, N. R. (2016). Effect of investigative laboratory approach and expository method on acquisition of science process skills by biology students of different levels of scientific literacy. *African Journal of Education, Science and Technology*, 3(1), 236-243.
- Nyaboke, R., Kereri, D., & Nyabwari, L. (2021). Competence-based curriculum (CBC) in Kenya and the challenge of Vision 2030. *International Journal of Education, Technology and Science*, 1(4), 155-169.
- Ramsden, P. (2003). *Learning to teach in higher education*. Routledge.
- Sanders, S. (2019). A Brief Guide to Selecting and Using Pre-Post Assessments. *National Technical Assistance Center for the Education of Neglected or Delinquent Children and Youth (NDTAC)*.
- Shivaraju, P. T., Manu, G., Vinaya, M., & Savkar, M. K. (2017). Evaluating the effectiveness of the pre- and post-test model of learning in a medical school. *National Journal of Physiology, Pharmacy and Pharmacology*, 7(9), 947.